

Title: “Mechanical Testing of Scaled Cellulose Nano-Fiber based Composites made using Micro-RTM Process”

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Abstract

The plant-derived cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) have very high mechanical properties compared to other natural fibers, even approaching the properties of inorganic reinforcing fibers. The CNF based polymer composites, because of their being biobased and biodegradable and not having some drawbacks of the usual natural-fiber based composites, are an alternative ‘green’ material available for automotive and other engineering applications. The composites made from this new type of CNF reinforcement are likely to have very good strength compared to other kinds of composites including the natural-fiber composites. However, such an assertion about the mechanical properties of scaled-up composites made from CNF is yet to be investigated through experiments. In this paper, the scaled CNF composites were made from the highly porous form of CNF reinforcement that was created using the freeze-drying process. This paper discusses the results of the tensile and three-point bending tests conducted with CNF-based and other composites. The composite samples were made using a micro-RTM (resin transfer molding) process after using the freeze-dried CNF and other fibers as reinforcement, and epoxy as the matrix. The causes of failure of such samples are also discussed.